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USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation This article is written about the appropriate use of modern technologies in the study and teaching of English, as well as the teacher's search for himself, feeling responsible, innovating in the lessons, making sure that the lesson is interesting and lively.

Key words: innovations, technologies, efficiency, specialization, information communication, telecommunications.

Abstract. This article deals with the use of innovative technologies in the study and teaching of English and the creativity of teachers, responsibility, the introduction of new methods that make the lesson interesting and lively.

Key words: innovations, technology, efficiency, specialization, mass media, telecommunications.

At present, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. A number of English language experts are introducing new methods and ways of learning English. This will certainly increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. Learning with technology has several unique benefits. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps language learners to keep up with the times and move forward. Technology is gradually replacing traditional education. Today, television programs regularly

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air a number of new programs and shows that help teach English.

It should also be noted that today new methods of using modern innovative technologies are being introduced in Uzbekistan to improve the effectiveness of training. For example, a student who is taught a foreign language based on multimedia has the opportunity to develop four skills and learn by both seeing and listening to interesting materials. In addition, the student may guess the meaning of some words by watching live action and try to understand it. Undoubtedly, the use of modern technologies of computers, radio, CD, DVD in any foreign language lessons will further promote the educational process and allow the younger generation to master foreign languages faster.

The fact that some teachers do not know how to apply and do not use technology in English classes leads to some boredom of students. It is for this reason, that is, in order not to extinguish the student's enthusiasm, that the use of technology and at least a computer during the lesson provides an increase in the student's interest. After all, educational and methodological materials prepared taking into account the age, interest, abilities, mastering the lessons of the student will certainly be effective. On the contrary, if we as teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast videos, songs or texts containing complex words to primary school students or show them through multimedia and computers, then when we show educational materials consisting of very simple texts to middle and high school students or groups, students' interest in learning the language gradually fades, and they do not learn the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to lower grades, loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students.

It follows that the main task is not only to use technology during the lesson, but to

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be able to use it in its place and ensure that the use of technology serves to increase the student's knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, that is, the International European Education Standards, the four competencies of teaching English: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) are conducted in English, it is important to use technology effectively and correctly during classes. For example, listening lessons have their own rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the student to understand the audio material they are listening to and be able to analyze it without difficulty.

To do this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare an audio playback environment in which listeners must provide a calm environment, and the teacher must pay attention to the quality of the reproduced audio and the soundness of the sound amplifiers. , as well as the exercises to be done before and after the audio is played, the audio should be ready and students should be provided with handouts.

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